

Fabrication of CNTs/Al composite with enhanced dispersion pre-treatment

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Abstract

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were considered as perfect reinforcements with excellent strength, modulus and physical properties. Dispersing CNTs into matrix, especially the metal matrix was a challenge work due to CNTs clusters and poor wettability. An enhanced pre-treatment combined with Sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) treatment and Natural rubber (NR) treatment was used to disperse CNTs. The results demonstrated that SDBS could effectively de-bundle CNTs and NR could stable the SDBS treated CNTs. The 0.5 wt.% pre-treated CNTs reinforced 2009Al was fabricated in powder metallurgy route. The strength was enhanced about 20 %, which implied good load transfer efficiency of the CNTs.

1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted much attention as a class of ideal reinforcements for composites because of their extremely high elastic modulus (around 1 TPa) and strength (30-100 GPa) as well as good thermal and electrical properties [1-2]. By incorporating the CNTs into appropriate matrixes, enhanced reinforcing effects are expected to be achieved.

Though main research efforts have been focused on the CNTs reinforced polymer or ceramic matrix composites in the past decade, a few groups have dedicated to the fabrication of the CNTs reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs). Dispersion of the CNTs in the metal matrix is one of key challenges for successful fabrication of the CNTs reinforced MMCs because the CNTs clusters are easily induced as a result of their large aspect ratio and strong Vander Vals force.

Powder metallurgy (PM) route has been used to fabricate the CNTs MMCs because it is easier to incorporate the CNTs into the metal matrix compared with cast processing, which has the problems of poor wetting properties and large density differences between CNTs and metal melt. In the conventional PM route, the CNTs were usually pre-functionalized to reduce the entangled CNTs clusters and thus improve the homogeneity degree of CNT dispersion in the metal matrix [3]. However, the functionalization of the CNTs inevitably opens either the ends or the sidewalls of the CNTs, disrupting the π -electron system and impairing the electronic and thermal properties [4].

For overcoming this problem, high energy ball mill (HEM) process has been used to fabricate CNTs-metal composite powders. During the HEM process, the CNTs could be uniformly distributed into the metal matrix [5]. Unfortunately, HEM causes severe damage to the CNTs, such as amorphous carbon production, length and wall thickness reduction due to high energy input and long treatment time. Thus, developing new PM routes for fabricating CNTs reinforced MMCs is highly desirable.

Sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS), a commonly used surfactant, was reported to be able to effectively disperse single wall CNTs in aqueous solution [6]. Unfortunately, SDBS was hard to be removed. Natural rubber (NR) was also reported to be able to disperse CNTs to some extent [7]. However, it was difficult to de-bundle CNTs clusters. In this article, the CNTs were firstly pre-treated by SDBS aqueous solution and then sonicated with natural rubber (NR). The aim of this article was to establish a new route for fabrication of CNTs/Al composites with homogeneous CNTs dispersion.

2 Experimental

2.1 CNTs pre-treatment

As-received CNTs (95-98% purity) provided by Tsinghua University, had entangled morphologies with an outer diameter of 10-20 nm and a length of several microns (Fig. 1). For dispersing CNTs with optimal SDBS aqueous concentration, 50 mg CNTs were sonicated with 50 ml SDBS aqueous solution with concentrations of 0, 0.1, 5, 10, 20 and 50 mg/ml, respectively, for 4 h. The suspensions were kept for 1 month for sedimentation observations. Then CNTs sedimentations were filtered using filter papers with pore sizes from 30 to 50 μm , and then the mass of the sedimentations were measured for comparison. The supernatant fluid with the least sedimentations was dropped onto aluminum foils for SEM observation. Fig. 2 shows dispersion treatment flow schematic for the CNTs. 400 mg CNTs treated by SDBS with the optimal concentration were filtered, dried and then introduced into a NR and petrol solution for 2 h sonicated treatment.

Fig. 1 Morphology of the as-received CNTs.

Fig. 2 Flow of CNTs pre-treatment.

2.2 Composite fabrication and characterization

80 g 2009Al powders 10 μm in size were dried at 413 K for 2 h, dropped into the CNTs suspensions and were mixed for 4 h. The as-mixed CNTs/Al composite were cold compacted, degassed at 773K

for 1 h and then hot-pressed at 833K for 1 h. Then the composite billet was hot-forged at 723K with a deformation ratio of 4:1. For comparison, the CNTs/Al composite with the CNTs treated by NR only and the matrix alloy were also fabricated with the same processing.

The CNTs distributions in the matrix under various fabrication conditions were examined using the optical microscopy (OM, Zeiss Axiovert 200MAT), field emission scanning electron microscopy (Leo Supra). The as-forged composites were solutionized at 768 K for 2 h, water quenched and then naturally aged for 4 days. Tensile specimens with a gauge length of 2.5 mm, a width of 1.5 mm and a thickness of 0.8 mm were machined from the as-forged composites perpendicular to the forge direction. Tensile tests were conducted at a strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature. For comparison, the tensile test of the 2009Al was conducted under the same conditions.

3 Results and discussion

Fig. 3 CNTs/SDBS suspensions kept for 1 month. With SDBS concentrations (mg/ml) of (a) 0, (b) 0.1, (c) 5, (d) 10, (e) 20 and (f) 50.

Fig. 3 shows the CNTs in SDBS aqueous solution with different SDBS concentrations kept for 1 month. The CNTs could not be dispersed in pure water (Fig. 3(a)), but they could be partially dispersed in the aqueous solution due to the presence of SDBS. For SDBS, except for the hydrophilic-hydrophobic interaction and the charge interaction, the presence of a phenyl group in the surfactant is suggested to provide superior dispersive ability due to π - π stacking interactions, despite being at the hydrophilic end of the molecule.

It is thought that the phenyl group plays a role in the initial separation of individual CNTs from a bundle, adsorbing laterally in the narrow space between adjacent CNTs. Thus, the CNTs were

dispersed in the suspension with ink-like color. However, as SDBS concentration increased to 50 mg/ml, the color of the suspension became lighter, which indicated that fewer CNTs remained in the suspension. This is due to attractive depletion interactions. Simulations with CNTs and surfactant micelles have shown these effects to depend on the length of the CNTs, with longer CNTs inducing greater depletions. Therefore, once the pressure exerted by the micelles is large enough, the CNTs are forced together preferentially to provide a larger reduction in the osmotic pressure.

Fig. 4 shows the mass of sedimentation in SDBS aqueous solution with different concentrations. The results were in accordance with the suspension experiment. The presence of SDBS could disperse CNTs at proper surfactant concentrations, between 5 mg/ml to 20 mg/ml. Very large surfactant concentration of 50 mg/ml deteriorated the CNTs dispersion. Especially, the SDBS/H₂O with a concentration of 5 mg/ml gave the smallest sedimentation and provided a good CNTs dispersion. Thus, the SDBS aqueous solution with concentration of 5 mg/ml was used for the CNT pre-treatment.

Fig. 4 Sedimentation ratios after SDBS/H₂O treatment with different concentrations.

Fig. 5 CNTs in the CNTs/ (5mg/ml) SDBS aqueous suspension.

Fig. 5 shows the SEM micrograph of the CNTs dispersion in the depletive suspension. It is indicated that CNTs were separated with each other by the SDBS molecules. That implied that CNTs could still be separated with each other even when the water was filtered out.

Fig. 6 0.5 wt.% CNTs/2009Al composites: (a) CNTs treated by SDBS combined with NR, (b) CNTs un-treated and (c) CNTs treated only by NR.

Fig. 6 shows the dispersed CNTs in CNTs/2009Al composites with different CNTs treatments. The CNTs treated by SDBS and NR led to a homogeneous dispersion. The CNTs were mainly dispersed along the aluminum grain boundaries as small bundles. The un-treated CNTs and the NR treated CNTs both remained a lot of large clusters. This indicates that the pre-treatment processing was effective to improve the uniformity of the CNTs. It mainly resulted from two reasons. First, SDBS could de-bundle large CNTs clusters. The CNTs clusters were de-bundled by the hydrophilic-hydrophobic interaction and charge interaction during the SDBS treatment processing, however the SDBS absorbed on the CNTs were not stable and the treated CNTs easily re-agglomerated when they were washed by water. Herein, the CNTs were filtered other than washed by water. After filtering, CNTs were separated with each other by surface-absorbed SDBS molecules, which reduced the re-agglomeration tendency of the CNTs. Second, NR had weak ability to debundle CNTs, however it could stabilize CNTs bundles. By absorbing onto the un-bundled CNTs surfaces, NR repelled the neighboring CNTs against agglomerating together. Thus, CNTs were dispersed uniformly along the

aluminum boundaries by the combination of the SDBS and NR treatment.

Fig. 7 Stress and strain curves of as-forged 2009Al and CNTs/2009Al composite under natural ageing condition.

Fig. 7 shows the tensile curves of the 2009Al matrix and the CNTs/2009Al composites. It is noted that the YS and the UTS were increased by incorporating CNTs into the matrix. The YS increased from about 300 MPa to about 350 MPa, while the UTS increased from about 400 MPa to 450 MPa. And the elongation decreased a little from 18 % to about 15%.

According to load transfer concept, the strength of the composites could be expressed by [8]:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m (1 + RV_{CNTs})$$

where σ_c , σ_m are strength of the composites and matrix alloy respectively. V_{CNTs} is volume fraction of the CNTs. R is strengthening efficiency of the CNTs. The larger the R is, the higher efficient the load transfer is.

Substituting the strength of the matrix (300MPa) and the composite (350MPa) into the equation, the coefficient of load transfer was calculated to be 26.6, which was very close to the value of 27~28 in uniformly distributed CNTs reinforced copper matrix composites fabricated by molecular mixing technique [8]. It means that the CNTs were highly efficient to transfer load and the homogenous CNTs distribution was beneficial to the strengthening.

4 Conclusions

(1) SDBS aqueous combined with NR pretreatment was successful to fabricate uniformly dispersed CNTs reinforced aluminum alloy powders, mainly due to the good cluster dispersing ability of SDBS and stability of the

NR. After forging process, the CNTs aligned along the grain boundaries of the matrix.

(2) The CNTs reinforced aluminum alloy composite was strengthened compared with the aluminum alloy. The calculated load transfer coefficient demonstrated the homogeneously dispersed CNTs were highly efficient to transfer load, which was beneficial to strength enhancement.

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